

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART VI. SEPARATION FROM RARE EARTHS. CAMPHORIC ACID

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It is shown that camphoric acid precipitates thorium quantitatively in an ammonium acetate buffer. The approximate p_H has been determined as 4.2 and higher. Cerite earths are precipitated by the reagent at p_H 6.2 and higher. Separation of thorium from the cerite earths has been achieved by a double precipitation at p_H 4.4. The procedure has been utilised for the estimation of thorium in monazite extracts. The behaviour of a few other elements Ni, Co, Ti, etc., towards the reagent has also been investigated.

In the course of an extended search for reagents for the separation of thorium from rare earth elements in monazite, we have investigated the behaviour of camphoric acid. The acid is comparatively strong and only buffering with ammonium acetate brings about complete precipitation of thorium. A number of common elements (*vide infra*) interfere along with Ce^{IV} , Ti, and Zr. Rare earth elements even in equal proportions contaminate the thorium precipitate, but on a second precipitation this interference disappears. The thorium precipitate is then remarkably pure up to 1:15 ratios of ThO_2 to R_2O_3 . In this way thorium in monazite can be easily estimated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Estimation of Thorium.—A stock solution of thorium nitrate (10 ml., equivalent to 0.0749g. of ThO_2) was diluted to 100 ml. and heated to boiling; then 5 ml. of 10% ammonium acetate and 100 ml. of a boiling 1% solution of camphoric acid were added. The precipitate which was bulky at first soon became more compact and settled rapidly. It was filtered while hot through a 11 cm. Whatman No. 41 and washed with 0.1% camphoric acid solution, partially dried and ignited to the oxide. Two successive estimations gave the values 0.0749 and 0.0748 in good agreement with the theoretical.

Composition and Properties of the Precipitate.—The precipitate was finally washed with hot water and dried to constant weight at 105°. Ignition tests on the dried residue indicated a composition approximating to $O=Th(OOC)_2C_8H_{14}, 3H_2O$. It was also noticed that thorium camphorate was markedly soluble in concentrated ammonium acetate solution, which was further investigated as follows. The precipitate was shaken up for several hours with 100 ml. quantities of acetate solutions of different concentrations. The liquid in each case was filtered through a dry filter and the filtrate (50 ml.) was tested for thorium with the following results.

When, however, 0.5 g. of camphoric acid was added to the acetate solution in each case, no colorimetric test for thorium could be obtained in the filtrate up to 5% ammonium acetate solution. These semiquantitative investigations reveal that although thorium camphorate is appreciably soluble in concentrated ammonium acetate solution, buffering with moderate quantities leads to no significant loss of the metal and the presence of excess camphoric acid renders precipitation quantitative.

TABLE I

Solubility of thorium camphorate in 100 ml. of ammonium acetate solutions.

Ammon. acetate soln.	Reagent used.	Reaction.	Amount of ThO ₂ in 100 ml. of the filtrate.	Remarks.
10%	Oxalic acid	Precipitate	42.5 mg.	The precipitate is washed and ignited to oxide
5	Do	Slight turbidity	6.4	Comparison with standard
1	(a) Do	No turbidity	...	...
	(b) Alizarin S	Pink colour	2.0	Colorimetric.
0.5	Do	Very slight pink		
0.25*	Do	Coloration hardly visible	1.0	Do ...

Corresponds to the quantity of the buffer in an actual precipitation.

Influence of p_H on the Completeness of Precipitation and Removal of Cerite Earths.—Preliminary tests on the precipitation of thorium by the acid showed that below p_H 4.2 it was incomplete and above p_H 6.2 the cerite earths started to precipitate. The optimum p_H was then about 4.4. As has been already stated, camphoric acid is a moderately strong acid and in 1% solution has a p_H 3.4. To establish the requisite p_H of 4.4 in the final liquid for the complete precipitation of thorium, the thorium solution (or thorium cerium mixture) should have a p_H of $\approx$ 5.4. This was achieved by making the solution neutral to Congo red, diluting to 100 ml. and then adding 5 ml. of 10% ammonium acetate solution.

Separation from Cerite Earths.—Even at a p_H of 4.4, which is far from the p_H 6.2 for the precipitation of cerite earths, contamination by the latter occurred and for the complete removal a second precipitation became necessary. For this purpose the precipitate first obtained was only partially washed, then dissolved in hot 1:4 nitric acid. The solution was neutralised to Congo red with dilute ammonia and the precipitation of thorium was repeated. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Vol. of Th (NO₃)₄ taken = 10 ml.

No.	Wt. of R ₂ O ₃ added.	Wt. of ThO ₂ present.	Wt. of ThO ₂ estimated.	Error.
1	0.053 g.	0.0749 g.	0.0767 g. 0.0747*	+0.0018 -0.0002
2	0.159	0.0749	0.0761 0.0749*	+0.0012 ...
3	0.318	0.0749	0.0769 0.0750*	+0.0020 +0.0001
4	0.632	0.0749	0.0781 0.0746*	+0.0032 -0.0003
5	0.795	0.0749	0.0791 0.0745*	+0.0042 -0.0004

Double precipitation.

Interference from Other Elements.—A number of common elements are precipitated either partially or completely along with thorium by the reagent; Ni and Co do not interfere. The behaviour of other elements is summarised below.

Ti, Ce^{IV}, Fe^{III}, and Al are completely precipitated.

Pb is partially precipitated. The lead salt dissolves on boiling with water, but small quantities always accompany thorium even in a triple precipitation.

Be is partially precipitated in the cold and completely on boiling.

Cu and U are incompletely precipitated.

Estimation of Thorium in Monazite.—Thorium in the phosphate-free neutral monazite extract (cf. Part I of this series, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 457) was estimated with the reagent after a double precipitation. The following results were obtained.

TABLE III

No.	Monazite soln. taken.	Wt. of ThO ₂ in nitrobenzoic acid.	estimated with reagent.	Error.
1	10 ml.	0.0810 g.	*0.0809 g.	-0.0001
2	20	0.1620	*0.1621	+0.0001

*Mean of four consecutive determinations.

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